

Benefits and Challenges of Digitalizing Education for Teachers and Students: The Case of Foreign Language Training

Dandan LI¹, Oksana BOIKO², Nataliia KOTENKO³ & Tetiana ZHYROVA⁴

¹ Corresponding Author, Kharkiv Polytechnic Institute, Kharkiv, UKRAINE
lidandan0415@gmail.com

ORCID: 0000-0002-6816-6096

² Zaporizhzhia National University, Zaporizhzhia, UKRAINE
super-ksenichik05@ukr.net

ORCID: 0000-0002-8850-1066

⁴ State University of Trade and Economics, Kyiv, UKRAINE
kotenkono@outlook.com

0000-0002-2675-6514

⁵ State University of Trade and Economics, Kyiv, UKRAINE
zhyrova@outlook.com

ORCID: 0000-0001-8321-6939

Article Information

Submission	19/03/2024	Revision received	28/06/2025
Acceptance	15/08/2025	Publication date	01/10/2025

Keywords:

Information technologies

Online platforms

Distance learning

Surveys

Testing

Chatbot

Abstract: This study aims to identify the advantages and disadvantages of digitalization from the perspectives of students and teachers, as well as its impact on learning effectiveness. A range of methods, including analysis, synthesis, induction, deduction, survey, testing, as well as statistical and logical comparison, were employed. To determine the effectiveness of distance learning and online learning platforms, 98 students at a Ukrainian state university were tested after completing an elective course. To determine the advantages and disadvantages of digital technologies from the perspectives of students and teachers, an online survey was conducted with 98 students and 39 teachers. The results of the tests indicated the effectiveness of the online learning platform as an auxiliary tool for a face-to-face course. However, there was no difference between the test results and the form of education (face-to-face, distance, or hybrid). Among the advantages of digital technologies, teachers noted the automation of processes, assistance in visualizing educational materials, and access to scientific sources. Students noted the convenience of distance learning, the clarity of video materials, and the ability to use learning materials at any time thanks to mobile applications, online platforms, and artificial intelligence. The disadvantages of using most information technologies in education were high cost, unreliable personal data protection, and the risk of dishonesty.

Anahtar Sözcükler:

Bilgi teknolojileri

Online platformlar

Uzaktan öğrenme

Anket

Ölçme

Sohbet robotu

Eğitimin Dijitalleştirilmesinin Öğretmenler ve Öğrenciler İçin Yararları ve Zorlukları: Yabancı Dil Eğitimi Örneği

Özet: Bu çalışma, dijitalleşmenin öğrenci ve öğretmen algıları ile öğrenme etkinliği açısından avantaj ve dezavantajlarını belirlemeyi amaçlamaktadır. Analiz, sentez, tümevarım, tümdengelim, anket, test, ayrıca istatistiksel ve mantıksal karşılaştırma gibi çeşitli yöntemler kullanılmıştır. Uzaktan eğitim ve çevrim içi öğrenme platformlarının etkinliğini belirlemek amacıyla, bir devlet üniversitesinde seçmeli bir dersi tamamlayan 98 öğrenciye test uygulanmıştır. Dijital teknolojilerin avantaj ve dezavantajlarını öğrenciler ve öğretmenlerin bakış açısından belirlemek için ise 98 öğrenci ve 39 öğretmenle çevrim içi bir anket yapılmıştır. Test sonuçları, çevrim içi öğrenme platformunun yüz yüze derslere yardımcı bir araç olarak etkili olduğunu göstermiştir. Bununla birlikte, test sonuçları ile eğitim türü (yüz yüze, uzaktan veya hibrit) arasında herhangi bir fark bulunmamıştır. Dijital teknolojilerin avantajları arasında öğretmenler; süreçlerin otomatikleştirilmesini, eğitim materyallerinin görselleştirilmesine katkısı ve bilimsel kaynaklara erişimi belirtmiştir. Öğrenciler ise uzaktan eğitimin sağladığı kolaylığı, video materyallerinin açıklığını ve mobil uygulamalar, çevrim içi platformlar ve yapay zekâ sayesinde öğrenme materyallerine her zaman erişebilme olanağını vurgulamıştır. Eğitimde kullanılan çoğu bilgi teknolojisinin dezavantajları arasında ise yüksek maliyet, kişisel verilerin güvenilir biçimde korunamaması ve akademik dürüstlük riskleri öne çıkmıştır.

To Cite This Article: Li, D., Boiko, O., Kotenko, N., & Zhyrova, T. (2025). Benefits and challenges of digitalizing education for teachers and students: The case of foreign language training. *Novitas-ROYAL (Research on Youth and Language)*, 19(2), 54–68. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17036219>

1. Introduction

Since education is responsible for teaching new trends in various fields, the digitization of the economy and its spheres of influence has necessitated the need to train future workers in information technology. In turn, digital technologies have also influenced the education system, forcing all participants in the educational process to adapt to new conditions (Cantner et al., 2022). Thus, digital education has become a necessary component of the higher education system, and the rapid development of the latest technologies has altered approaches to the educational process, which differ significantly from classical pedagogical methodologies. In particular, employers expect future professionals to be flexible, versatile, eager to learn, creative, analytical, and able to make independent decisions, in addition to possessing professional knowledge. This competency-based approach has become the foundation for transforming the education system, which is adapting to the modern labor market's requirements. The paradigm shift in teaching methodology is driven by the rapid adoption of digital technologies, which have replaced numerous repetitive processes previously handled by employees and now performed by computer programs.

Digitalization has had a direct impact on education, as numerous information technology tools have enabled the optimization of the learning process (Cengiz & Kaçar, 2024; Yıldız, 2024; Zorba, 2020). In particular, the possibilities for searching knowledge have expanded thanks to global search engines, mathematical calculations have been simplified with the help of computer programs, and the possibilities for visualizing educational material, communication, and other applications have improved. However, there is a question of whether it is advisable to replace established pedagogical methods with digital analogues and how this affects the degree of learning and the acquisition of professional skills. The digitization of education is critical in the context of training foreign language specialists and developing their communication and intercultural skills. Therefore, the study aims to identify the advantages and disadvantages of digitizing education from the perspectives of teachers and students.

2. Literature Review

Digitalization is being rapidly introduced in all industries as it optimizes business processes, expands opportunities, and promotes economic growth. However, the education sector, especially in conservative countries, has long been resistant to digital transformation. For example, in Germany, despite the government's policy of developing digital education since 2000, the state of implementation of information processes in practice was extremely low until the pandemic. Moreover, as of 2019, fewer than 2% of German university students rated the digitization of education as progressive, and Germany ranked last in the digitalization of education index among European countries. However, funding for the development of information technology was sufficient. This is due to the prejudiced attitude of the German population towards information technology, stemming from concerns about protecting the privacy and interests of citizens (Stolz, 2023). An analysis of the digital adoption index among EU countries revealed no clear correlation between economic development, geographic location, and digitalization. Estonia, the Netherlands, and Finland were among the first countries to adopt the latest technologies prior to the COVID-19 pandemic. However, they differed in these criteria (Beblavý et al., 2019). Moreover, numerous studies have shown that the development of digitalization is influenced not only by investment but also by public policy, public trust in innovation, and the protection of the

interests of citizens' rights in the implementation of digital technologies (Komljenovic et al., 2024; Omodan, 2024; Piriomalli, 2023; Zorba, 2023).

The COVID-19 pandemic, which led to the rapid introduction of online education and electronic platforms for learning and communication, has become a revolutionary impetus for the global digitalization of the education system (Alnagrati et al., 2024; Erdem Coşgun & Savaş, 2023). The dynamics of the educational process restructuring in the online format, on the one hand, indicated the readiness of educational institutions to implement digitalization, and on the other hand, demonstrated the role of motivation for the development of new technologies (Murphy et al., 2022). Another aspect was the readiness of higher education institutions' managers to perform administrative work remotely and provide conditions for distance learning (Semenets-Orlova et al., 2022). Thus, quarantine conditions have become an excuse to ignore the warnings of conservatives and skeptics about the use of technological innovations in education. On the other hand, it is the gradual investment over two decades in the development of digital infrastructure and the legal regulation of digitalization that has become the basis for the successful implementation of distance learning in such a short time (Weller, 2020; Alazzam et al., 2023).

In education, digital technologies range from automatic computing to blockchain technologies and artificial intelligence. Generally speaking, digitalization tools are divided into those focused on students, teachers, and administrative purposes. In particular, students utilize online platforms, applications, chatbots, video materials, virtual reality, and programs for communication, self-education, and self-assessment. For teachers, information technology offers the ability to delegate automated processes, select materials tailored to individual needs, evaluate student learning outcomes, predict future achievements, facilitate continuous professional development, and communicate remotely. For administrative purposes, technologies are used to create curricula and thematic programs, store data on student performance, teacher workload, and group formation, among other things (Holmes & Tuomi, 2022).

Among the advantages of digitalization are increased access to the material base, workload optimization for teachers, simplified communication with students, an individualized approach to students, and a reduced likelihood of assessment errors. However, the development of information technology in higher education requires investment in digital infrastructure, reformatting faculty responsibilities, training in high-tech skills, and effective management of personal data security. A brief overview of the types of digital technologies and their applications in education is presented in Table 1.

Although the diversity of digital technologies in education is considerable, higher education institutions integrate them in different ways, depending on their financial and technical capabilities. While platforms and programs for distance learning are widespread and used in almost every university, technologies such as blockchain and the Internet of Things are still in their early stages of development. Although the prospect of blockchain implementation offers the possibility of a secure environment for sharing information on students' certification and academic performance in the labor market, its cost and high-tech nature pose barriers (Alsobhi et al., 2023). Investment is often an obstacle to the comprehensive digitalization of educational institutions, partly due to a lack of awareness of the benefits of various technologies. Another factor is the large number of competing and constantly updated offers on the information technology market, which reduces the trust of managers in the field of digitalization and privacy security. Thus, higher education institutions are faced

with a difficult choice of digital technology proposals that must be justified from a pedagogical, organizational, security, and financial perspective. Besides, such problems also negatively affect the quality and sustainability of education. Given that higher education institutions are critical change agents, playing a highly critical role in shaping the future (Arikan & Zorba, 2024), such as educating future leaders, policymakers, teachers, scientists, and engineers. Therefore, it is essential to evaluate the benefits and drawbacks of modern information technologies to inform the selection of digital tools that cater to the needs of teachers and the expectations of students.

Table 1.

Application of digital technologies in education

Type of digital technology	Application	Programs
Platforms for distance learning	Distance learning, lectures, conferences, and online communication	Zoom, Google Meet, Moodle.
Database of scientific data	Search and publication of scientific articles, monographs, and research results.	Scopus, Web of Science, PubMed, Web of Knowledge
Artificial intelligence	Language learning, automatic translation, class scheduling, assessment, and forecasting of students' progress,	Intelligent Tutoring Systems, Google Translate, Reverso, GPT, Language generation system
Mobile applications	Testing; Learning the language; Practicing skills.	Duolingo, Driver knowledge tests
Big data	Analysis and forecasting of students' behavior and achievements, teachers' workload, and trends in the work of the higher education institution	Data Future, Microsoft Azure Machine Learning, Hadoop.
Blockchain	Increases the confidentiality and transparency of data on student performance and the quality of educational programs	Cryptography to protect data from tampering and criminal intrusion
Virtual reality	Creation of laboratories and practical materials, development of practical skills	Simulators, computer games, virtual laboratories
Machine learning	Assessment of student performance, constant feedback between student and teacher, prediction of further learning outcomes, recommendations for individual programs	Platforms for online testing, analyzing student performance, attendance, and the use of various teaching methodologies
Video materials	Visual demonstration of educational material	Video tutorials, lecture presentations, and 3-D visualization

3. Method

3.1. Research Design

The study employed a range of methods, including analysis, synthesis, induction, deduction, survey, testing, and statistical and logical comparison. The research design consisted of two parts: testing and surveys, conducted in 2023-2024. The testing was conducted to determine the effectiveness of distance learning and an online platform with a chatbot. The training course is presented in Appendix A and took four weeks.

3.2. Participants

The convenience sampling method was employed to select research participants, as this method allows researchers to collect data from samples “that are both easily accessible and willing to participate in a study” (Teddlie & Yu, 2007, p. 78). Accordingly, 98 first-year students majoring in management at Mykhailo Drahomanov Ukrainian State University, who took the course “Fundamentals of Management under Uncertainty,” participated in the study. All students enrolled in the undergraduate course Fundamentals of Management under Uncertainty. Additionally, each participant volunteered to participate in the data collection process, and confidentiality was ensured through the use of participant anonymity. The second part of the study included a survey with the participation of 98 students and 39 teachers from the same university, who were part of the same student group, to identify the advantages and disadvantages of digitalization of education from the perspectives of both students and teachers.

3.3. Data Collection and Analysis

After completing the course, the participants were tested, which included a combination of machine-based assessment, open-ended written answers, and an oral interview with the teachers. The testing format included 10 test questions on the online platform, two questions with written, detailed answers, and two questions for an oral interview (an example of the test is provided in Appendix B). The maximum number of points was 60, with open-ended questions worth 10 points each and test questions worth 2 points each. Table 2 summarizes the data analysis process.

Table 2.
Data Analysis Procedure

Aspect	Details
Evaluation Criteria	< 15 points → Unsatisfactory level 15–30 points → Low level of knowledge 30–45 points → Sufficient level 45–60 points → High level
Maximum Score	60 points
Assessment Procedure	Test results obtained via an online platform. Open-ended and oral questions were independently evaluated by four professors of the Department of Management (developers of the course).
Student Grouping Method	Random assignment (excluded the possibility of distribution based on academic performance).
Groups	Group I (n = 21): Online platform with chatbot Group II (n = 19): Online course Group III (n = 18): Face-to-face course Group IV (n = 19): Hybrid course (online lectures + face-to-face seminars) Group V (n = 21): Face-to-face course using an online platform
Statistical Analysis Software	ANOVA (Analysis of Variance) STATA 12.1
Significance Level	p < 0.05

Accordingly, a total number of points less than 15 indicates an unsatisfactory level, 15-30 signifies a low level of knowledge of the course, 30-45 is considered a sufficient level, and 45-60 points is a high level. The test results were obtained using an online platform, with open-ended and oral questions independently evaluated by four professors of the Department of Management who developed the course. Depending on the use of digital technologies for teaching the course, students were divided into five groups: Group I (n = 21) included learning through an online platform with a chatbot, Group II (n = 19) - an online course, Group III (n = 18) - a face-to-face course, Group IV (n = 19) - a hybrid course (a combination of online lectures and face-to-face seminars), and Group V (n = 21) - a face-to-face course using an online platform. The students were divided into groups using a

random method, which excluded the possibility of distribution based on academic performance. For the statistical comparison of the results, the method of analysis of variance ANOVA was used using STATA 12.1. The reliability of the results was accepted at a significance level of $p < 0.05$. The survey was conducted online using a Google Form. Participation in the survey was voluntary and confidential. The survey included the following questions about attitudes towards different types of digitalization in education: “What types of digital technologies are used at your university?”, “Which types of digitalization do you think have a positive impact on education?”, “What are the advantages and disadvantages of the most common types of digitalization?”. The survey results are presented graphically.

4. Results

The advantages of the digitization of education for participants in the process of training foreign language specialists include increased accessibility of educational resources and adaptability of learning, creation of new opportunities for personalization of education, improvement of the quality of learning, improvement of interaction and communication in the educational field, and development of digital literacy skills. Data security concerns drive the challenges of digitization, the need to develop digital literacy skills, and the requirement for adaptation to new technologies.

Table 3.

Test results at the end of the course with statistical analysis using ANOVA analysis of variance

Group	Training format	n	M	SD	<i>p</i> between groups	df	F
I	Online platform with a chatbot	21	27.8	6.0	$P_I - P_{II} < 0,001^*$ $P_I - P_{III} < 0,001^*$ $P_I - P_{IV} < 0,001^*$ $P_I - P_V < 0,001^*$		
II	Online course	19	38.3	4.9	$P_{II} - P_I < 0,001^*$ $P_{II} - P_{III} < 0,166$ $P_{II} - P_{IV} < 0,099$ $P_{II} - P_V < 0,001^*$		
III	Full-time course	18	39.9	4.9	$P_{III} - P_I < 0,001^*$ $P_{III} - P_{II} < 0,166$ $P_{III} - P_{IV} < 0,377$ $P_{III} - P_V < 0,001^*$	94	42.6
IV	Hybrid course	19	40.5	5.0	$P_{IV} - P_I < 0,001^*$ $P_{IV} - P_{II} < 0,099$ $P_{IV} - P_{III} < 0,377$ $P_{IV} - P_V < 0,001^*$		
V	Full-time course + online platform	21	50.6	4.7	$P_V - P_I < 0,001^*$ $P_V - P_{II} < 0,001^*$ $P_V - P_{III} < 0,001^*$ $P_V - P_{IV} < 0,001^*$		

The proposed course “Fundamentals of Management under Uncertainty” was elective, so students were motivated to study it. Depending on the learning format, students were divided into five groups: Group I - learning through an online platform and a chatbot, Group II - online learning, Group III - a face-to-face course, Group IV - a hybrid course (a combination of face-to-face and distance learning), Group V - a combination of a face-to-face course and learning through an online platform. The course curriculum was the same for all students, with the same amount of learning materials, including presentations and video lessons. However, the online learning platform offered round-the-clock access to all learning

materials and the possibility of self-assessment through tests. The test results after the course are presented in Table 3.

As can be seen from the test results, the best results were demonstrated by students of Group V, who combined a face-to-face course with an online learning platform. The average score in Group V was 50.6 ± 4.7 , which was statistically different from all groups of students and corresponded to a high level of knowledge. Instead, no significant difference was found between the results of students in groups II, III, and IV, indicating that there was no significant difference between face-to-face and distance learning. At the same time, significantly worse results were demonstrated by students in Group I, who used only an online platform and a chatbot for their studies, with a mean of 27.8 ± 6.0 . Moreover, the low level of knowledge was observed in this group, as evidenced by both the written and oral parts of the test. Additionally, students in Group I highlighted the low quality of the chatbot's answers to clarifying questions, which led to the answers in the training tests on the online platform being perceived as axiomatic without a clear understanding of the content. Students of Group I showed the lowest level of satisfaction with the course, as only 25.2% of students rated the course positively. Group I students attributed these results to the lack of live communication with the teacher and the inability to clarify unclear points using a chatbot.

As a result, by the end of the course, the activity of Group I students on the online platform had significantly decreased. The highest level of satisfaction with the course (78.4% of students surveyed) was observed among students in Group IV, which combined distance and face-to-face classes, due to the balance of convenience provided by the distance format and live communication. In addition, the test results in Group IV were also at a sufficient level (40.5 ± 5.0), which had a positive impact on the learning of the course material. The level of satisfaction with the course among students in Group V was also high, as 75.3% of the surveyed students gave a positive evaluation of the course. This was made possible by the opportunity to review the course material at a convenient time on the online platform. Another positive aspect was the possibility of self-testing on the platform, which greatly simplified the test part of the final exam for students in Group V (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Level of satisfaction with the course

As can be seen from the results, the online platform of the created course had a positive impact on learning effectiveness only when there was a teacher in group V. Satisfaction with the course in this Group of students was also high, which was due to the possibility of self-repeating the

material and assessing progress on the online platform. Instead, there was no significant difference between the distance and face-to-face teaching formats, as evidenced by the absence of a significant difference in test results among groups II, III, and IV, with average scores of 38.3 ± 4.9 , 39.9 ± 4.9 , and 40.5 ± 5.0 , respectively. However, the low results of students in Group I indicated that without teacher support, the online platform was effective only for solving test tasks. Instead, the interview and the written part of the test revealed superficial knowledge of course topics when using the online platform without teacher support in Group I. Although in Group I it was proposed to use a chatbot instead of a teacher, this approach did not yield positive results, despite the development of a chatbot for the course being financially and professionally challenging. Moreover, the availability of the chatbot caused dissatisfaction among the students who used it, as the chatbot did not meet their expectations. This is due to the low specificity of chatbots to individual student needs.

To determine the attitudes of teachers and students towards different types of digitalization and their application in education, an online survey was conducted among 98 students and 39 teachers of the Mykhailo Drahomanov Ukrainian State University. The questions concerned teaching and assessment methods that are being introduced or are already actively used in the educational process. Figure 2 illustrates the results of a survey conducted among teachers and students regarding their level of satisfaction with digital technologies in education.

Figure 2. Results of the survey of students and teachers

According to the survey results, machine learning, scientific and metric databases, and online learning platforms received the highest favorable ratings among teachers. According to the surveys, machine learning is widely used in assessing student achievement. Teachers noted that this form of assessment helps them understand the problematic aspects of learning materials and allows for a quick and efficient general analysis of knowledge. This, in turn, reduces the workload of teachers, and updating test tasks is not a difficult task. Students also positively evaluated machine learning for grading, justifying their response with the objectivity and transparency of the assessment. Among the disadvantages of machine learning, teachers highlighted the potential for errors that could result in incorrect positive

answers or student dishonesty. This disadvantage is offset by the constant updating of the test database and the use of fuzzy sets for assessment (Bakhov et al., 2021).

Among the digital tools with a positive impact on learning, more than 65% of teachers chose online platforms and scientific and metric databases to search for information. Among the disadvantages of online platforms, teachers noted the high cost, the time-consuming nature of creating the platform, and the need for ongoing maintenance. That is why the availability of online platforms is rare in practice. Students also positively assessed the capabilities of online platforms; however, our study revealed that online platforms are less effective without teacher supervision. This drawback can be eliminated if the online platform is used as an auxiliary learning tool. Scientific metric databases were often used and positively evaluated by teachers as a reliable source of information, allowing them to highlight their own achievements. However, only 35.2% of students positively assessed the usefulness of scientific and metric databases. Specifically, they identified closed access to popular scientific databases and a lack of search skills as obstacles to working on scientific websites. It is worth noting that some universities have met students' needs by providing them with access to paid scientific and metric databases from the libraries of higher education institutions.

The most popular information technologies among students were distance learning on Zoom and Google Meet platforms, video lessons, and mobile applications. This indicates a positive attitude among students towards the online learning format and their ability to access learning materials at any time through online platforms. Instead, teachers were more skeptical about online learning, as they considered it less effective and difficult for the teacher. To address this shortcoming, it is advisable to use hybrid learning models that include both distance and face-to-face classes. Our study also confirms that the combination of online and offline learning formats is most preferred by students (Group IV), who noted that they learn better due to the combination of different teaching formats.

As for video lessons, students also expressed greater satisfaction with this medium than teachers. In particular, teachers did not choose video lessons because of the large amount of time and effort required to create video content. The use of mobile apps and programs for learning and testing was more popular among students than among teachers. This was due to the convenience for students, in particular, who used apps to learn the language and take tests. Teachers considered such tools to be ineffective and noted the lack of a structured approach to learning through mobile apps, which, in their opinion, leads to a gradual demotivation of students to study. Artificial intelligence was popular among students, with more than 40% of respondents giving it a positive assessment. Students utilized artificial intelligence to learn foreign languages, facilitate automatic translation, and generate automatic writing. Teachers were mostly negative about artificial intelligence, which was due to a lack of trust in GPT chat and its capabilities. Teachers expressed distrust in students' integrity when using GPT chat and spent more time checking texts for independent writing.

Big data and cloud storage were rated higher among teachers, who noted the positive impact of these tools in practice, namely storing data on students, their performance, and attendance. Big data aids in managing the educational process by creating schedules, thereby freeing teachers from organizational tasks. Big data was less prevalent among students, primarily due to the low interest in the organizational aspects of higher education within the student community. The disadvantages of big data and cloud storage were unreliable protection of personal data and the need for constant technical support and software updates. To overcome the security flaw of personal data leakage and falsification, it is necessary to use the latest

blockchain technologies that provide transparency and protection against third-party intrusion. However, blockchain technologies are practically not used in higher education institutions, and teachers and students are not familiar with their benefits. This fact is mainly due to the high cost of blockchain technologies. Virtual reality also received one of the lowest scores among both students and teachers. This is due to the high cost of the technology and the low feasibility of its implementation for most areas of study. However, the use of simulations in some areas, such as medicine, is revolutionary and needs to be implemented.

5. Discussion

Our research has revealed the importance and effectiveness of digital technologies in the education system. However, when introducing new technologies, it is advisable to focus on their overall impact on student performance and the attitude of participants in the educational process towards innovations. Thus, despite the positive assessment of online platforms among students and teachers, their effectiveness was found to be low when used without teacher support. This confirms the fact that no information technology can replace teachers (Chan & Tsi, 2024). However, when used properly, online platforms have demonstrated promising results in helping students assimilate material and enabling teachers to visualize it more effectively.

In terms of the learning format, our study did not find a significant difference between the effectiveness of online, offline, and blended learning. However, Kumari et al. (2021) emphasized the lower effectiveness of online learning compared to face-to-face learning from both pedagogical and psychological perspectives. Such discrepancies may indicate the optimization of distance learning in recent years, as well as the positive impact of student motivation on online learning outcomes (Tang et al., 2021). Student motivation plays a crucial role in achieving goals and influences student behavior based on the expected outcomes over time. The authors found that low levels of satisfaction and perspective are reflected in students' motivation to acquire visible knowledge in the present, rather than focusing on future achievement. Thus, when focusing on future achievements, students are more motivated and gradually move towards the goal, while focusing on present knowledge gives a sense of slow development, which negatively affects the desire to continue learning. That is why it is crucial to establish clear, long-term learning expectations in pedagogical approaches. This will help maintain students' attention throughout the course, which is essential for effective learning and is often impossible without teacher involvement.

Most digital tools open up new opportunities for teaching and assessment, increase receptivity through visualization, and reduce teachers' workload through automated processes. However, one of the disadvantages is the high cost of software, which seems unjustified for some technologies, such as a chatbot designed to assist students in our study, which ultimately proved ineffective in practice. Another disadvantage is the potential for unfair use of digital technologies, such as GPT chat for writing term papers, which can compromise the objectivity of student performance assessment (Dai et al., 2023). Another weakness is the protection of personal and confidential data, which reduces trust in information technology among both teachers and students. Although a robust blockchain security technology can improve the reliability of data protection, its high cost hinders its use in the education system (Alsobhi et al., 2023).

6. Conclusion

The analysis of the advantages and disadvantages of digitalization of education from the perspectives of students and teachers revealed that information technology presents new

opportunities when utilized effectively. Specifically, the study found that online learning platforms are effective only when a teacher is involved and, in combination with teacher support, have a positive impact on the quality of learning and student satisfaction. Instead, the use of an online platform with a chatbot, lacking teacher support, results in a low level of knowledge and fails to meet students' expectations. At the same time, no significant difference was found in the learning of educational material regardless of the form of education (face-to-face, distance, or hybrid).

Among the advantages of information technology, teachers highlighted the automation of processes in assessment, scheduling, and other organizational tasks, as well as the visualization of educational materials and the ease of finding reliable scientific sources. The disadvantages included the high cost of most digital technologies, which can be inappropriate in some instances, personal data protection issues, and the risk of student dishonesty in machine-based assessments and the use of GPT chat. Students highlighted online learning, online platforms, video lessons, artificial intelligence, and mobile learning applications as positive aspects of digitalization. This trend indicates that students prioritize convenience in learning above all else. Machine learning was also positively perceived by students due to its objective nature. Instead, the use of scientific and metric databases among students was limited due to the lack of access to the sites. Personal data security was also a significant drawback from the perspective of both students and teachers. To address the issue of personal data security, utilizing blockchain technologies is advisable; however, their high cost poses a significant obstacle. Students and teachers rated virtual reality in education the least positively due to its high cost and the limited use in some educational fields, such as medicine.

Ethical Issues

Regarding the ethical considerations of the research, an informed consent letter was distributed to all participants prior to their involvement. The consent form was formulated to furnish participants with adequate information about the study, an understanding of the research aims, and to ensure voluntary participation. Matters concerning anonymity and confidentiality were also addressed and explained to the participants.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declared no conflict of interest.

Data Availability

The data presented in this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request. The data are not publicly available due to privacy reasons.

References

- Alazzam, F. A. F., Shakhathreh, H. J. M., Gharaibeh, Z. I. Y., Didiuk, I., & Sylkin, O. (2023). Developing an information model for e-commerce platforms: A study on modern socio-economic systems in the context of global digitalization and legal compliance. *Ingenierie des Systèmes d'Information*, 28(4), 969–974. <https://doi.org/10.18280/isi.280417>
- Alnagrat, A. J., Che Ismail, R., Syed Idrus, S. Z., Abukhatowah, U. A. I., & Gopalan, V. (2024). The impact of digitalisation strategy in higher education: Technologies and new opportunities. *International Journal of Business and Technopreneurship (IJBT)*, 12(1), 79–94. <https://ejournal.unimap.edu.my/index.php/ijbt/article/view/995>

- Alsobhi, H. A., Alakhtar, R. A., Ubaid, A., Hussain, O. K., & Hussain, F. K. (2023). Blockchain-based micro-credentialing system in higher education institutions: Systematic literature review. *Knowledge-Based Systems*, 265, 110238. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.knosys.2022.110238>
- Arikan, A., & Zorba, M. G. (2024). Raising pre-service English language teachers' awareness of sustainable development goals through literary texts. *International Journal of Sustainability in Higher Education*, 25(8), 1681–1695. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJSHE-06-2023-0256>
- Beblavý, M., Baiocco, S., Kilhoffer, Z., Akgüç, M., & Jacquot, M. (2019). Index of readiness for digital lifelong learning: Changing how Europeans upgrade their skills. *CEPS Final Report November 2019*. Brussels: Centre for European Policy Studies. Retrieved from <http://aci.pitt.edu/id/eprint/101025>
- Cantner, U., Dauchert, H., Hölzle, K., & Stolz, C. (2022). Challenges on the digitalisation of the universities in the European higher education area: The case of Germany. In B. Broucker, R. Pritchard, C. Milsom, & R. Krempkow (Eds.), *Transformation fast and slow: Digitalisation, quality and trust in higher education* (pp. 78–102). London: Brill. https://doi.org/10.1163/9789004520912_005
- Cengiz, B. C., & Kaçar, I. G. (2024). Pre-service EFL teachers' online language teaching and their TPACK development. *Novitas-ROYAL (Research on Youth and Language)*, 18(1), 48–67. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10972972>
- Chan, C. K. Y., & Tsi, L. H. (2024). Will generative AI replace teachers in higher education? A study of teacher and student perceptions. *Studies in Educational Evaluation*, 83, 101395. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.stueduc.2024.101395>
- Chiu, T. K., Xia, Q., Zhou, X., Chai, C. S., & Cheng, M. (2023). Systematic literature review on opportunities, challenges, and future research recommendations of artificial intelligence in education. *Computers and Education: Artificial Intelligence*, 4, 100118. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.caeai.2022.100118>
- Dai, Y., Liu, A., & Lim, C. P. (2023). Reconceptualizing ChatGPT and generative AI as a student-driven innovation in higher education. *Procedia CIRP*, 119, 84–90. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procir.2023.05.002>
- De la Vall, R. R. F., & Araya, F. G. (2023). Exploring the benefits and challenges of AI-language learning tools. *International Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities Invention*, 10(1), 7569–7576. <https://doi.org/10.18535/ijsshi/v10i01.02>
- El Koshiry, A., Eliwa, E., Abd El-Hafeez, T., & Shams, M. Y. (2023). Unlocking the power of blockchain in education: An overview of innovations and outcomes. *Blockchain: Research and Applications*, 4(4), 100165. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bcra.2023.100165>
- Erdem Coşgun, G., & Savaş, P. (2023). Unveiling the metamorphosis: English teachers' shifting identity in the context of post-COVID-19 distance education. *Novitas-ROYAL (Research on Youth and Language)*, 17(2), 66–79. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10015822>
- Holmes, W., & Tuomi, I. (2022). State of the art and practice in AI in education. *European journal of education*, 57(4), 542–570. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ejed.12533>
- Komljenovic, J., Birch, K., Sellar, S., Bergviken Rensfeldt, A., Deville, J., Eaton, C., & Williamson, B. (2024). Digitalised higher education: key developments, questions, and concerns. *Discourse: Studies in the Cultural Politics of Education*, 46(2), 276–292. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01596306.2024.2408397>
- Kučak, D., Juričić, V., & Đambić, G. (2018). Machine learning in education-a survey of current research trends. In B. Katalinic (Ed.), *29th DAAAM International Symposium*

- on *Intelligent Manufacturing and Automation* (pp. 406–410) Austria: DAAM Publication. <https://doi.org/10.2507/29th.daaam.proceedings.059>
- Kumari, S., Gautam, H., Nityadarshini, N., Das, B. K., & Chaudhry, R. (2021). Online classes versus traditional classes? Comparison during COVID-19. *Journal of education and health promotion*, 10(1), 457. https://doi.org/10.4103/jehp.jehp_317_21
- Miranda, J., Navarrete, C., Noguez, J., Molina-Espinosa, J. M., Ramírez-Montoya, M. S., Navarro-Tuch, S. A., Bustamante-Bello, M. R., Rosas-Fernández, J. B., & Molina, A. (2021). The core components of education 4.0 in higher education: Three case studies in engineering education. *Computers & Electrical Engineering*, 93, 107278. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compeleceng.2021.107278>
- Murphy, V. L., Iniesto, F., & Scanlon, E. (2022). Higher education's digitalization: Past, Present and Future. In A. Kaplan (Ed.), *Digital transformation and disruption of higher education*. (pp. 9–21). Cambridge: Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/9781108979146>
- Omodan, B. I. (2024). Redefining university infrastructure for the 21st century: An interplay between physical assets and digital evolution. *Journal of Infrastructure, Policy and Development*, 8(4), 3468. <https://doi.org/10.24294/jipd.v8i4.3468>
- Piromalli, L. (2023). Higher education policy in practice: digitalization and the governance reform in an Italian university (1988-2021). *History of Education*, 52(6), 937–952. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0046760X.2022.2141355>
- Semenets-Orlova, I., Klochko, A., Tereshchuk, O., Denisova, L., Nestor, V., & Sadovyi, S. (2022). Special aspects of educational managers' administrative activity under conditions of distance learning. *Journal of Curriculum and Teaching*, 11(1), 286–297. <https://doi.org/10.5430/jct.v11n1p286>
- Stolz, K. (2023). The impact of digitalisation on higher education teaching in Germany. In L. Leišytė, J. R. Dee, & B. J.R. van der Meulen (Eds.), *Research handbook on the transformation of higher education* (pp. 281–294). Cheltenham, UK: Edward Elgar Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.4337/9781800378216.00028>
- Tang, Y. M., Chen, P. C., Law, K. M., Wu, C. H., Lau, Y. Y., Guan, J., He, D., & Ho, G. T. (2021). Comparative analysis of Student's live online learning readiness during the coronavirus (COVID-19) pandemic in the higher education sector. *Computers & Education*, 168, 104211. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2021.104211>
- Teddle, C., & Yu, F. (2007). Mixed methods sampling a typology with examples. *Journal of Mixed Methods Research*, 1(1), 77-100. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1558689806292430>
- Weller, M. (2020). *25 years of ed tech*. Canada: Athabasca University Press. <https://doi.org/10.15215/aupress/9781771993050.01>
- Williamson, B. (2018). The hidden architecture of higher education: Building a big data infrastructure for the 'smarter university'. *International Journal of Educational Technology in Higher Education*, 15, 1–26. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s41239-018-0094-1>
- Yıldız, C. (2024). ChatGPT integration in EFL education: A path to improved speaking self-efficacy. *Novitas-ROYAL (Research on Youth and Language)*, 18(2), 167–182. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13861137>
- Zorba, M. G. (2020). Understanding English language learners' interpretations of cultures: The case of digital photographs. In *Conference Proceedings EDUNOVATIC 2020* (pp.182–186). Madrid: Adaya Press. <https://doi.org/10.58909/adc20576280>
- Zorba, M. G. (2023). Exploring EAP students' conceptualization of sustainable development goals: Implications for higher education. *Novitas-ROYAL (Research on Youth and Language)*, 17(2), 112–127. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10015841>

Appendices

Appendix A. Elective course on Fundamentals of Management under Uncertainty

Topic 1: Fundamentals of strategic planning and crisis adaptation.

Topic 2: Development of anti-crisis programs in conditions of uncertainty and war.

Topic 3: Search for international partners, charitable and volunteer organizations to support anti-crisis measures.

Topic 4: Monitoring of crises and evaluation of methods of counteracting crisis phenomena.

Topic 5: Training of staff in the algorithm of actions in crises.

Topic 6: Changes in management processes under conditions of uncertainty.

Topic 7: The role of specialized centers and advisory bodies to combat crisis challenges.

Topic 8: Inter-sectoral cooperation in dealing with crisis processes.

Topic 9: Cooperation with the authorities under conditions of uncertainty.

Appendix B. Testing Items

1. What are the problems of management in wartime?
 - Problems of logistics
 - Safety of working conditions
 - Interruptions in supply
 - Shortage of personnel
2. What are the main reasons for unsatisfactory adaptation to crisis conditions?
 - Lack of strategic goals
 - Delay in decision-making
 - Over-reliance on established business norms
3. What are the key areas of management transformation in a crisis?
 - Organization of the management structure
 - Support for teamwork
 - Creating an adaptive business model
4. The main strategic directions of management change?
 - Decentralization of management
 - Centralization of management
5. What are the main requirements for teamwork in the face of uncertainty?
 - Adaptability
 - Flexibility
 - Ability to make decisions depending on the situation
 - Reputation management
6. What are the main requirements for business models under uncertainty?
 - Clear mathematical models
 - Transparency of production processes
7. The role of international cooperation in the face of uncertainty:
 - Access to new markets
 - Exchange of experience
 - Increasing competitiveness
8. The role of technology in crisis management:
 - Analysis and forecasting of market changes
 - Assistance in decision-making
 - Adaptation to changes
 - Quick search for information
 - Simplified communication
 - Automatic monitoring of business processes
9. Main objectives of cooperation with the authorities:
 - Monitoring of changes in legislation under conditions of uncertainty
 - Predicting risks associated with government actions
 - Preparation of scenarios in accordance with changes in legislation
 - Communication with the authorities to find joint solutions
10. The main objectives of inter-sectoral cooperation in crisis management:
 - Exchange of experience
 - Expansion of partner networks
 - Exchange of technologies
 - Increasing competitiveness
11. Suggest a step-by-step strategy for managing a company under conditions of uncertainty, and justify your answer.

12. Compare centralized and decentralized management, explain under what conditions it is advisable to carry out centralized management of the company, and under what conditions decentralized management is advisable.
13. Describe the mechanism for the development of international and intersectoral cooperation in the face of uncertainty.
14. Development of innovations or preservation of financial and resource sustainability: what to choose in conditions of uncertainty? Justify your answer.